

TRAIN4EU

Transforming ReseArch & INnovation
agendas and support in 4EU+

H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-1-2020

Project no.: **101016674**

Start date of project: **1 January 2021**

Duration of project: **36 months**

Deliverable

Reference number and title:

**D 6.2 Report of collaborative work with other alliances
on lessons learned, and associated recommendations,
Governance for Joint Collaboration**

Name of lead beneficiary:

University of Copenhagen

Due date:

30. November 2023

Submission date:

22. November 2023

Dissemination level: Public

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement No 101016674.

Deliverable overview

Deliverable title: Report of collaborative work with other alliances on lessons learned, and associated recommendations, Governance for Joint Collaboration

Work Package: WP6 Governance for Joint Collaboration [M 6-35] / Univ. of Copenhagen

Deliverable summary: D 6.2 consists of three sections.

Section 1 introduces scope and objectives, tasks and timeline for milestones and deliverables for Work Package 6 (lead UCPH; all). This section is adapted from section 1 in D 6.1 *Protocol, Governance for Joint Collaboration*.

Section 2 covers Task 6.2: *Implementing joint learning, innovation and policy recommendations across European University Alliances* (M13-35). Task 6.2 is addressed through 3 subtasks:

- subtask 6.2.1: explore and expand collaboration on R&I support functions within 4eu+ based on activities and outcomes of WP1-5
- subtask 6.2.2: explore joint modes of collaboration and coordination for maximizing the exploitation of project outcomes across European University Alliances
- subtask 6.2.3: produce two policy briefs on R&I support function transformations, submitted through WP7 DEC

Section 3 outlines perspectives on TRAIN4EU's post-project phase, including pathways to sustainable collaboration on R&I transformations within 4eu+ and across European University Alliances.

Prepared by: D 6.2 is prepared by WP6 lead and TRAIN4EU project manager Miriam Kockvedgaard Zeitzen (MKZ), University of Copenhagen.

WP6 MS / Deliv. M 13-35	MS / Del. versions	Date	Prepared By
Milestone 5	Final version	28. June 2022	MKZ
Milestone 7	Final version	30. April 2023	MKZ
Milestone 8	Final version	31. Aug. 2023	MKZ
Deliverable 6.2	First draft	20. Oct. 2023	MKZ
Deliverable 6.2	Final version	22. Nov. 2023	MKZ

Dissemination level: Public

Table of Contents

Deliverable overview	2
Table of Contents.....	3
1. TRAIN4EU WP6 - Governance for Joint Collaboration	4
WP6 Scope & objectives	4
WP6 Tasks & subtasks.....	4
WP6 Timeline & TRAIN4EU Milestones	5
2. WP6 Task 6.2: Implementing joint learning, innovation and policy recommendations across European University Alliances	6
Subtask 6.2.1: Explore and expand collaboration on R&I support functions within 4eu+	7
Subtask 6.2.2: Explore joint modes of collaboration across and beyond EUAs.....	8
Milestone 5: Meeting with other alliances	8
Milestone 7: Status on collaboration with other alliances	11
SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023	11
Collaborations with European University Alliances	16
Subtask 6.2.3: Producing 2 ERA policy briefs on R&I support function transformations	17
D7.6 ERA Policy brief 1	17
D7.7 ERA Policy brief 2	17
3. TRAIN4EU post-project pathways.....	17
Investment pathways for R&I dimensions of EUAs	18

1. TRAIN4EU WP6 - Governance for Joint Collaboration

WP6 Scope & objectives

WP6's scope is to explore 'joint structures across European Universities, facilitating collaboration in activities, obstacles, and solutions that could be common to all alliances, as well as clustering activities to share best practices on research and innovation' (from Horizon2020 SwafS-32-2020 call)

WP6 is TRAIN4EU's main externally oriented work package. It seeks to upscale intra-alliance to inter-alliance collaboration, to boost collaboration on research support functions within and between European University Alliances (henceforth EUAs). as well as engage with the wider European university landscape and the European Commission (henceforth EC).

WP6 does not have a set team, but draws on the expertise of project members, in particular the Steering Committee. WP6 stakeholders include, on an intra-alliance level, 4eu+ Secretary General and Management Committee, on an inter-alliance level, SwafS project partners in the FOR-EU R&I subgroup, and on a European level, REA & DG RTD. WP6 is led by TRAIN4EU project manager.

WP6's objectives are, as per TRAIN4EU Grant Agreement, Annex 1 (Part A), section 1.3.3:

- using baseline and practices assessments coming out WP1-5, exploring which common features across universities in the alliance facilitate excellence, as well as collaboration on R&I support functions, what constitutes obstacles and what solutions to these might be.
- maintaining a dialogue and participating in joint dissemination and coordination activities with sister European University Alliances to ensure widespread collaboration and learning across alliances.

WP6 Tasks & subtasks

WP6's main aim is to strengthen collaborative work with other European University Alliances on lessons learned, best practices and associated recommendations in terms of R&I support function transformations, based on cases identified, baselined, analysed and potentially piloted within the core topical WPs 1-5. To achieve this aim, WP6 has been subdivided into two main tasks:

Task 6.1 / Deliverable 6.1 (M 12): *Identifying and analysing common drivers of, obstacles for, and solutions to challenges and collaboration in R&I support functions.*

- Task 6.1 addresses WP6 objective #1: "using baseline and practices assessments coming out of WP1-5, exploring which common features across universities in the alliance facilitate excellence, as well as collaboration on R&I support functions, what constitutes obstacles and what solutions to these might be."
- The main outcome of Task 6.1 is **D 6.1 Protocol Governance for Joint Collaboration**, submitted M12. D6.1 built on WP1-WP5 task 1.1 - 5.1 outcomes, outlined in D1.1 – D5.1 (submitted M6), and initial outcomes from tasks 1.2 - 5.2, outlined in D1.2 – D5.2 (submitted M14 - M30).
- D6.1 mapped emerging collaboration domains in terms of common drivers, obstacles and solutions for collaboration from R&I support function cases selected for baselining, best practice assessment and innovation across the topical WP1-5. It also prepared a framework for assessing the efforts and the learnings they draw forward.

Task 6.2 / Deliverable 6.2 (M 35): *Implementing joint learning, innovation and policy recommendations across European University Alliances.*

- Task 6.2 addresses WP6 objective #2: “*maintaining a dialogue and participating in joint dissemination and coordination activities with sister European University Alliances to ensure widespread collaboration and learning across alliances.*”
- The main outcome of Task 6.2 is the present report D6.2 on the collaborative work with other EUAs on lessons learned, best practices and associated recommendations.

The focus of Task 6.2 / D6.2 is to strengthen joint collaboration on R&I transformations and facilitate governance for joint collaboration within 4eu+ and across and beyond the European University Alliances. The upscaling of intra-alliance collaboration to inter-alliance collaboration has the further aim to contribute to future policy development concerning European University Alliances.

Task 6.2 builds on Task 6.1 by gathering inspiration and suggestions for common solutions for collaboration in R&I support functions from the D6.1 protocol. Concrete solutions and inter-alliance collaborative potentials will mainly be drawn from lessons learned and expected results of Task 1.2 - 5.2 / D1.2 – D5.2 (submitted M14 - M30) and Task 1.3 – 5.3 / D1.3 – D5.3 (due M35) in WP1 - WP5.

The scope of Task 6.2 reflects the level of collaboration with particularly the first generation EUAs SwafS projects, as well as joint alliance engagement in EU focal domains such as the new ERA.

WP6 Timeline & TRAIN4EU Milestones

As per TRAIN4EU Grant Agreement, Annex 1 (Part A), section 1.3.2 List of Deliverables, 1.3.3 Work Packages Descriptions, and 1.3.4 List of Milestones, the following timeline for WP6 activities, milestones and deliverables, incl. the two joint WP7 policy briefs, was set up:

Figure 1: TRAIN4EU WP6 timeline

Task 6.2 covers a span of 23 months, from M13 (Jan. 2022) to M35 (Nov. 2023). To effectively manage the long-running Task 6.2. activities, they will be closely aligned to TRAIN4EU milestones, as per TRAIN4EU Grant Agreement, Annex 1 (Part A), section 1.3.4. List of milestones:

Milestone number	Milestone title	WP number	Lead beneficiary	Due (Mns)	Means of verification
MS 1	Kick-off meeting	WP8	1 - UCPH	M 2	Minutes of kick-off meeting emailed to partners
MS 2	First outline of protocols for WP1-5	WP1-5	1 - UCPH	M 4	Drafts circulated to all WP leads
MS 3	First outline of protocol for WP6	WP6	1 - UCPH	M 9	Drafts circulated to all WP leads
MS 4	Result of the baseline process - short list of transformations to be used for piloting	WP1-5	1 - UCPH	M 12	List circulated
MS 5	Meeting with other alliances	WP6	1 - UCPH	M 18	Résumé from meeting circulated
MS 6	Status on planned piloting of new activities	WP1-5	1 - UCPH	M 24	Status on planned piloting of activities; status report from WP leads circulated.
MS 7	Status on collaboration with other alliances	WP6	1 - UCPH	M 28	Status report ready, incl. identification of potential joint activities
MS 8	Outline of WPs final report ready	WP1-7	1 - UCPH	M 32	Outlines circulated

Figure 2: TRAIN4EU Milestones

2. WP6 Task 6.2: Implementing joint learning, innovation and policy recommendations across European University Alliances

Task 6.2 addresses WP6 objective #2 "maintaining a dialogue and participating in joint dissemination and coordination activities with sister European University Alliances to ensure widespread collaboration and learning across alliances" through three subtasks:

- ❖ subtask 6.2.1: explore and expand collaboration on R&I support functions within 4eu+ based on activities and outcomes of WP1-5
- ❖ subtask 6.2.2: explore joint modes of collaboration and coordination for maximizing the exploitation of project outcomes across and beyond EUAs
- ❖ subtask 6.2.3: produce two policy briefs on R&I support function transformations to be submitted within WP7 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

Subtask 6.2.1: Explore and expand collaboration on R&I support functions within 4eu+

WP6 is TRAIN4EU's externally oriented WP, focusing on building collaborative spaces and sharing learnings with other EUAs, as well as working closely with the EC as its major external stakeholder. To boost inter-alliance collaboration, intra-alliance collaboration must also be boosted through WP6.

In subtask 6.2.1, focus has been on creating a platform for exploiting transformations of R&I support functions, reflecting the Horizon 2020 SwafS-32 call text Transformation Modules, in alignment with overall project objectives of developing a focused and transversal collaboration within different R&I support function domains in 4eu+. During the project lifetime, new collaborative possibilities have opened up in terms of both partners and topics, which might not previously have been explored.

Please refer to the WP1-WP5 deliverables D1.3-D5.3, due M35, for detailed descriptions of these collaborative domains, which reflect both potentialities and concrete opportunities for R&I communities across 4eu+'s six participating partner universities.

Subtask 6.2.1 feeds into TRAIN4EU's central challenge, which is to contribute to making 4eu+ a truly comprehensive alliance in terms of the various dimensions of collaboration. As part of its brief, WP6 has sought to support TRAIN4EU project members' work in exploring multiple pathways to link inter-alliance collaboration on research, innovation and societal engagement to the collaborative work already developed in 4eu+ in the ERASMUS+ funded educational domains.

WP6 thus shares the central objective of TRAIN4EU, which is to contribute to achieving comprehensive collaborations, covering all university missions, to unlock synergies and the full potential of 4eu+. On an alliance level, communities of practices are beginning to form in the fields covered by the project, and they are expected to continue to develop after TRAIN4EU ends.

In the final phase of the project, project members are working to consolidate lessons learnt for future collaboration, including potentials for piloting transformations collaboratively at operational (university) level, strategic (alliance) level, and policy (European) level, with the overall effect of more comprehensive collaboration within 4eu+.

TRAIN4EU has identified a series of indicators in relation to expected impacts from deeper cooperation in 4eu+, to help facilitate future synergies between Horizon Europe and Erasmus+. On a university level, impact indicators include demonstrating, based on best practice, the variety and adaptability of transformation efforts within a local context. The interplay between best practice and initiatives by the local administration aims to make transformations both dynamic and robust.

On an alliance level, impact indicators include facilitating the exchange of knowledge and developing models for cooperation between universities' staff within both programmes. This includes alignment of procedures for project management, as Erasmus+ and Horizon Europe programmes currently are under the responsibility of different administrative offices/units at local level. On a European level, it includes providing input to the EC on how to develop recommendations for sharing research infrastructures, as well as contribute to broader and increased mobility of researchers and students across universities in Europe, based on future networks for European research infrastructures.

Please refer to WP1-WP5 deliverables D1.3-D5.3 (M35) for outlines of intra-alliance collaboration indicators, as well as progress on reaching them within the project lifetime or beyond.

Subtask 6.2.2: Explore joint modes of collaboration across and beyond EUAs

In the TRAIN4EU Grant Agreement, Annex 1 (Part A), section 1.3.3. Work package descriptions, WP 6, task 6.2, it is stated that:

“In this task, we coordinate and organise activities such as seminars, workshops and other forms of exchanges, to ensure joint collaboration and learning across our own and sister European Universities Alliances. Based on this joint learning process, we aim to produce a joint set of common lessons learned and policy recommendations and messages on how to enhance R&I collaborations among European universities.

The 17 alliances (ARQUS, CHARM-EU, CIVICA, CIVIS, ECIU, EDUC, EPICUR, EU-CONEXUS, EU4Art, EUGLOH, EUTOPIA, FORTHEM, 4EU+, SEA-EU, UNA-Europa, UNITE! and YUFE), have agreed by the time of the submission of the SwafS proposals, that they will ensure joint collaboration across projects in the form of a Forum of European Universities (FOREU), face-to-face if possible, or on-line (M14), in order to discuss and share intelligence resulting from:

- Assessment of current practices, best practice and progress made / success stories on pilot implementation of long-term strategies
- Identification of barriers, legal, financial and regulatory which exists (local, regional or European)

By the end of the projects, the alliances expect to develop another shared activity with the European Alliances, where we will invite the new European University Alliances selected in the second call.”

As noted above, to handle the long-running task 6.2 activities (M13-35), they are closely aligned with TRAIN4EU Milestones (MS) 5 and 7, pertaining to WP6. The focus of MS 5 & MS7 is meetings with other alliances under the auspices of WP6.

Milestone 5: Meeting with other alliances

TRAIN4EU Milestone (MS) 5 - *Meeting with other alliances* – outlines the project’s first WP6 initiated inter-alliance meeting on collaboration within and across EUAs. It was submitted in M18. A résumé from the inter-alliance meeting was circulated to all WPs as a means of verification for MS 5.

The objectives of the event, and of MS 5, were to create a collaborative space for inter-alliance sharing based on the preliminary results and pilot actions coming out of WP 1-5 in tasks 1.2 – 5.2, as well as to discuss and share lessons learned to inform D7.6 Policy Brief 1, submitted M18.

The major outcome was the **4eu+ On-line Conference on Educational and Research infrastructure collaboration in European University Alliances**, held on 8. June 2022. Its scope was to cover both R&I and education dimensions of infrastructure, and explore their interfaces, to create synergy and strengthen the integration of the two core university dimensions within 4eu+.

It was a joint event involving TRAIN4EU as well as 4eu+’s Erasmus+ funded EUP project. It was coordinated by University of Copenhagen, under the auspices of WP6.

Programme

4EU+ ON-LINE CONFERENCE ON EDUCATIONAL AND RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
COLLABORATION IN EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY ALLIANCES – 8. JUNE 2022

09.00	Session 1. Plenary session: Educational and Research infrastructure collaboration in European University Alliances <i>Chair: Isabelle Kratz</i>	
	Welcome by 4eu+ Secretary-General Isabelle Kratz EC / EUI perspectives by <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tine Delva, Deputy Head of Unit Higher Education, DG EAC • Agnes Robin, Head of Sector Research Infrastructures, DG RTD 4eu+ perspectives by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sabine Bottin-Rousseau, EUP coordinator / Sorbonne • Bo Jellesmark Thorsen, TRAIN4EU coordinator / UCPH 	
09.45	Session 2. Parallel sessions: Where we are – infrastructure collaborations in European University Alliances	
	Joint Educational Infrastructure <i>Chair: Sabine Bottin-Rousseau</i>	Sharing Research Infrastructure <i>Chair: Bo Jellesmark Thorsen</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4eu+: Fabrice Moutte / EUP • CHARM-EU: Ferenc Takó & Jan Haarhuis • EPICUR: Thras Tsiatsos • Discussion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4eu+: Anne Jürgens / TRAIN4EU • UNA-EUROPA: Hideko Matsuo & Emilio Urbinati / UNA.RESIN • EUGLOH: Eric Cassan / EUGLORIAH • Discussion with Stijn Delauré, Policy Officer, DG RTD
10.50	BREAK	
11.00	Session 3. Parallel sessions: What we do – concrete practices and developments in European University Alliances	
	Practitioners in educational infrastructure <i>Chair: Fabrice Moutte</i>	Practitioners in research infrastructure <i>Chair: Anne Jürgens</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short presentations by practitioners from 4eu+, CHARM-EU & EPICUR • Plenary discussions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short presentations by practitioners from 4EU+, UNA-RESIN & EUGLOH • Presentations by CIVIS & EDUC • Plenary discussions
12.20	BREAK	
12.30	Session 4. Plenary session: Collaborations and synergies in infrastructure in European University Alliances <i>Chairs: Sabine Bottin-Rousseau & Bo Jellesmark Thorsen</i>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plenary discussions & concluding remarks going forward 	
13.00	End of meeting	

Figure 3: 4eu+ Infrastructure Conference programme, 8 June 2022 via zoom.

Participants

233 participants were registered for the conference through the on-line conference tool *Conference Manager*, used to organize the event by University of Copenhagen (UCPH). They included:

- 207 participants from a European University Alliance, of which
 - 106 participants were from 4eu+
 - 101 participants were from 26 further EUAs, representing two-thirds of 41 current European University Alliances (first and second generation). The 26 alliances were: ARQUS, AURORA, CHARM-EU, CIRCLE-U, CIVICA, CIVIS, CONEXUS, ECIUn, EDUC, EELISA, ENGAGE.EU, ENHANCE, ENLIGHT, EPICUR, ERUA, EU4ART, EUGLOH, EUniWell, EuroTeQ, EUTOPIA, RUN-EU, ULYSSEUS, UNA.EUROPA, UNITA, UNITE! and UNIVERSEH
- 21 participants were private participants / other affiliations.
- 5 participants were from the European Commission

Up to 170 participants attended the event, of which approx. 150 participated consistently for 3 hours, and 110 participated for 4 hours. Participants were evenly distributed in education and research parallel sessions.

Communication and dissemination

A news article featuring '4EU+ Conference: Learnings, challenges and obstacles in educational and research infrastructure' summarizes the main learnings of the event on the [4eu+ website](#). Topics addressed include Interconnection and digitalization in education; Building on experiences and adapting to needs; The importance of an inclusive research infrastructure definition; and Intensifying collaboration between Alliances.

DEC activities related to the event included:

Date	Channel	Link
5 May 2022	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6927950643106091008
5 May 2022	Twitter	https://twitter.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1522197391390265346
8 June 2022	Twitter	(20) 4EUplusAlliance on Twitter: " 📢 Our #online Conference on Educational and Research Infrastructure Collaboration has just started! Together with representatives of @Una_Europa, @eugloh19, @EpicurAlliance and @charm_eu we will share our experiences and lessons learned. 📄 https://t.co/Q5ZZjGDPI6 https://t.co/35KA45HsxV" / Twitter
9 June 2022	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/4EUplusAlliance/posts/1028579934695293
9 June 2022	Twitter	https://twitter.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1534795046389784576
9 June 2022	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6940602865262456832
9 June 2022	Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/4euplus_alliance/
23 June 2022	4eu+ newsletter	Follow-up article on conference 4EU+ Conference on Educational and Research Infrastructure Collaboration in European University Alliances
23 June 2022	4eu+ webpage	Follow-up article on conference 4EU+ Conference on Educational and Research Infrastructure Collaboration in European University Alliances

To further strengthen dissemination of conference outcomes, all presentations from the session speakers are made available to registered participants through [Conference Manager](#). To further strengthen network building, a full participant list will be available through [Conference Manager](#) to those participants who have accepted that their name appears on the list. Participants who have opted out will not receive the list in order to ensure compliance with GDPR regulations.

Milestone 7: Status on collaboration with other alliances

TRAIN4EU MS 7 *Status on collaboration with other alliances* outlines the project's inter-alliance meetings on collaboration across EUAs as of M28, under the auspices of WP 6. It was submitted in M28. A status report, which included identification of potential joint activities, was circulated to all WPs as a means of verification.

The objectives of MS 7 were to outline progress in terms of creating a collaborative space for inter-alliance sharing based on results and pilot actions coming out of WP 1-5 in tasks 1.3 – 5.3, as well as to outline progress in terms of enhanced R&I collaborations among European universities based on joint learnings with selected SwafS project partners from first generation EUAs.

The report represented work in progress, as the main WP6 driven event – a second meeting to boost collaboration with other alliances - will be the SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 held in Bruxelles on Nov. 30 - 1. Dec. 2023, at the time of submission of this report, D6.2, as per WP6's timeline above.

SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023

The SwafS Forum 2023 to be held in Bruxelles on 30. Nov.-1. Dec. 2023 accounts for WP6's second major action as outlined in task 6.2. As the event will take place after submission of the present D6.2 report, it can only be described in terms of planned activities and programme outlines; a more detailed description of outcomes will be available in the final periodic reporting for TRAIN4EU.

TRAIN4EU WP6 lead & PM MKZ / 4eu+ is in the organizing committee for the event, which is coordinated by CHARM-EU. 4eu+ will participate with a delegation of 8 people at the event.

TRAIN4EU WP 6 / 4eu+ is lead / co-lead / participating in 4 sessions at the SwafS Forum 2023:

- **Panel Session 30/11:** *From Agenda Setting to Implementation: Maximizing the Institutional Impact of the SwafS-Projects* (TRAIN4EU co-lead; lead FIT FORTHEM) – see below.
- **Workshop 2 30/11:** *Pilots and Action Plans: what are SwafS projects leaving for future developments of Alliances' R&I dimension* (TRAIN4EU lead; EUTOPIA co-lead) – see below.
- **Interactive poster session 30/11** (TRAIN4EU presentation): WP 3 lead Anne Jürgens / Univ. of Heidelberg will present a poster on 'Sharing Research Infrastructure', to create synergy with TRAIN4EU coordinator's presentation in the panel session – see below.
- **Roundtable 2 01/12:** *Research Ethics & Integrity: the role of new technologies;* Ladislav Kristoufek, Charles Univ. Vice Rector Research will speak on 'Publish or perish in the AI era.'

The forum is focused on strengthening collaboration between EUAs on lessons learned and project outcomes. It is addressed to representatives of the FOREU1 and FOREU2 alliances, to EC officials including SwafS project officers, as well as external stakeholders. The programme is as follows:

SCIENCE WITH AND FOR SOCIETY IN EUROPEAN UNIVERSITIES ALLIANCES: PROGRAMME

DAY 1

30 November

Morning - Policy | The future of R&I in European University Alliances

8:30 - 9:00:	Registration / Welcome / Initial photo
9:00 - 9:30 	Keynote: The EC Strategy to Support the Development of the European Alliances R&I Dimension Hybrid session
9:30 - 10:30 	Plenary Session: Looking to the Future: The European University Alliances R&I Dimension Hybrid session
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee break
11:00 - 11:30 	Plenary session: Assessment of the R&I impact of the European Universities alliances - reports by Commission and REA experts
11:30 - 12:30 	Panel session: From Agenda Setting to Implementation: Maximizing the Institutional Impact of the SwafS Projects Hybrid session
12:30 - 14:00:	Lunch break

Afternoon - Alliances | Showcasing the SwafS Outcomes: Best Practices and Lessons Learned

2:00 PM – 5:30 PM CET

14:00 - 16:00	Workshop sessions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop 1 – Advancing Our Common Science Agendas: building joint structures and support offices, pooling resources, capacity building, human capital, etc. • Workshop 2 – Pilots and Action Plans: what are the SwafS projects leaving for future developments of the Alliances' R&I dimension • Workshop 3 – Reforming Research Assessment • Workshop 4 – Inter- and Trans-disciplinarity in research management
16:00 - 16:30	Break
16:30 - 17:30	Interactive Poster Session Posters around 8 transformational modules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module 1: Developing a common R&I agenda and action plan • Module 2: Sharing resources & infrastructures • Module 3: Strengthening human capital • Module 4: Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic sector • Module 5: Mainstreaming Open Science practices • Module 6: Engaging citizens & society • Module 7: Exploring joint structures • Module 8: Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (others)

DAY 2

1 December

Morning | Inspiring the Future of R&I in Europe

9:00 - 9:45 	Plenary Session: Boosting Excellence within the European R&I Ecosystem through the European University Alliances Hybrid session
9:45 - 10:00	Break
10:00 - 11:30	Roundtable sessions with coffee Roundtable 1 – Taking care of the knowledge square: holistic support for a holistic handling of all four dimensions (broader vision) Roundtable 2 - Research Ethics & Integrity: The Role of New Technologies Roundtable 3 – Responsible R&I: Fostering Societal Engagement & Involving External Stakeholders Roundtable 4 – Green transition: sustainability on a green society in a digital era
11:30 - 12:30 	Plenary session: Conclusions from workshops and roundtables, next steps and final photo Hybrid session

Figure 4: SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 programme

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674.

Programme for the Panel Session on 30. November 2023:

Panel session: From Agenda Setting to Implementation: Maximizing the Institutional Impact of the SwafS-Projects

About: Discussion on the projects' capability to prompt institutional changes and transformational initiatives

Organizers: FORTHEM & 4EU+

Participants: Transform4Europe, SEA EU, RUN EU

Chair and Speakers

Chair / Speakers	RUN-EU	4EU+	Transf4Eur	SEA-EU	FORTHEM
Katarzyna Molek-Kozakowska, FIT FORTHEM Comm. specialist, Ass. Professor, Univ. of Opole 					

Keeping Notes: Agnese Rusakova (FORTHEM)

Abstract for the session

Transformative processes at European Universities cannot be designed on a drawing board and implemented top-down, especially when launched in a multicultural, multidisciplinary, cross-institutional and cross-European environment. European University Networks have made an impressive step forward to foster collaboration in the research, innovation, and knowledge transfer dimension by creating joint agendas and action plans, and by exchanging on best practices, setting up tools and structures to facilitate cooperation and bringing researchers together for joint project applications.

To progress from setting the agendas to sustainably implementing new formats and activities modelled and tested in the pilot phase requires time and resources. Some alliances have been faster in their implementation phase partly due to their ability to build on research partnerships in existence preceding the creation of the European University Alliance. Other alliances may need more time, particularly regarding the implementation of their research mission, as individual institutions in the alliance may be starting from quite diverse baseline conditions regarding research support structures, internal workflows, hierarchies, policies, and resources available.

In this session we want to discuss what is required to support faster implementation of actions developed regarding research, innovation, and knowledge transfer. We will evaluate how to implement actions without continued funding from the European Commission, how these actions promote an integrative approach to the all university missions, and what kind of enablers and barriers to implementation in a cross-culture and cross-institutional working environment are in place. Maximizing the impact means maximizing the enablers and resources and reducing the barriers, may they be institutional, national, or systemic.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674.

Structure of the session

Introduction to the focus of the session by the Chair	5 Minutes
Short pitch by each speaker on how SwafS-projects can really be institutional game changers including 1 good example for institutional/alliance level impact	20 minutes
Panel discussion will be based on the following guiding questions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strategies for strengthening human capital in Research and Innovation for the sustainability of the European Universities. (RUN-EU/RUN-EU PLUS) 2. Sharing Research Infrastructures in 4eu+: Drivers, obstacles and solutions to challenges and collaboration (4EU+/TRAIN4EU) 3. Lessons learned from implementing a cross-culture and cross-institutional working environment: enablers and barriers for a powerful impact (Transform4Europe/T4ERI) 4. Designing a sustainable research agenda: from solid, reliable and trust worthy research structure to the institutional commitment (SEA-EU/reSEArch-EU) 5. Funding of the Research Dimension of Alliances – how to move forward without a solid, flexible and targeted budget to implement results from the SwafS-projects and further develop actions related to R&I at alliance level (FORTHEM/FIT FORTHEM) 	25 minutes
Open discussion with the audience	10 minutes
Total	60 minutes

Programme for Workshop 2 on 30. November 2023:

Workshop 2 *Pilots and Action Plans: what are the SwafS projects leaving for future developments of the Alliances' R&I dimension*

Organisers: 4eu+ & EUTOPIA

Abstract

In Workshop 2 on *Pilots and Action Plans: what are the SwafS projects leaving for future developments of the Alliances' R&I dimension*, we will showcase key outcomes of the 4 SwafS projects presented, focusing on areas where the 4 alliances FILM-EU, UNA.EUROPA, EUTOPIA & 4eu+ have seen tangible progress and overall impact. Building on these key outcome outlines, speakers will engage with the audience in terms of 4 key questions, encouraging exchanges and interactive discussions, facilitated by the speakers. Through the presentations, interactive exchanges and a concluding Q&A session, we aim to underscore the SwafS projects' efforts to position European University Alliances as key contributors to the European R&I landscape, highlighting their unique value in complement to existing R&I collaborations. Our second aim is to advocate for future investment needs to allow European University Alliances to take forward their ambitions and fulfil their potential as drivers of the European Research Area, in Europe as well as globally.

Draft program:

- 14.00: Moderator welcomes speakers & participants, intro. workshop & sets policy context
- 14.10: Speakers present alliance topic & conclude with question for discussion
- 14.45: Moderator sums up & reiterates speakers' 4 questions to be discussed
- 14.50: Bio break & participants circulate to 4 boards in 4 corners w. 4 questions w. 4 alliances
- 15.00: Participants use floor to discuss 4 questions, speakers facilitate; at 15.25 return to seats
- 15.30: 4 groups/speakers present issues from discussion & Moderator leads Q&A session
- 16.00: Workshop ends

Speakers & Topics

EUTOPIA	UNA.EUROPA	FILM-EU	4eu+
Mattia Bellotti , EUTOPIA S.-G. & Sigríður Beck , MB TRAIN EUTOPIA	Sophia Karner , Senior policy officer UnaEuropa	Manuel José Damásio , Coordinator FILM-EU	Ladislav Kristoufek , Vice Rector Research Charles Uni., Prague
<i>Common R&I Agenda: From conceptualisation and pilot in SwafS project to implementation at alliance level</i>	<i>Una Europa's vision for research & innovation</i>	<i>Designing research agenda through joint initiatives: FilmEU Artistic res. Agenda</i>	<i>Cultivating the Future: Strengthening R&I Human Capital in the 4EU+ Alliance</i>
Session moderator: Elena del Giorgio , policy officer, 4eu+			

Workshop Rapporteur: Miriam Koktvedgaard Zeitzen, TRAIN4EU project manager

WP 3 poster for interactive poster session on 30. November 2023:

Figure 5: SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 TRAIN4EU WP3 poster

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674.

Collaborations with European University Alliances

At the TRAIN4EU Steering Committee meeting on 25. May 2023, WP6 lead & PM MKZ invited WP1-WP5 leads to contribute ideas on how to further widen the external scope of WP6, in relation to Task 6.2 potential joint TRAIN4EU activities with European University Alliances (EUAs) M19-M36. Examples of various ways WP1-WP5 activities articulate collaboration with other alliances were discussed, as partly outlined in MS 7. Please see D8.6 Minutes Steering Committee (5) (M29).

Potential WP1-5 activities pertinent to WP6 objectives were further discussed at the WP lead plenary meeting hosted by Univ. of Warsaw on 19 September 2023. Focus areas include coordination and organization of activities (seminars, workshops & other forms of exchanges) on R&I support, to ensure joint collaboration and learning, as well as production of joint set of common lessons learned on how to enhance R&I collaborations, across 4eu+ and among EUAs.

For example, WP 5 on Mainstreaming Open Science collaborates with CIVICA Alliance on FOR-EU LIB (cooperation of EUI university libraries). University of Warsaw Library and Sorbonne University Library represent 4EU+. In early 2023, FOR-EU LIB emerged within EUI libraries as a bottom-up initiative, coordinated by Sciences Po Library (Paris, France). There have been two meetings of the EUI librarians and three solutions were proposed to improve cooperation: FOR-EU Libraries mailing list (open to anyone who would be interested in the FOR-EU LIB network, an informal exchange group of librarians and researchers in European University Alliances), collaborative storage space (a shared and secure collaborative space reserved for members of our group established on pCloud), and mapping of library participation in Alliance projects (a questionnaire was sent to libraries).

Please refer to WP1-WP5 deliverables D1.3-D5.3 (M35) for descriptions of inter-alliance collaborations within WP1-WP5.

FOR-EU1 Research & Innovation subgroup

WP6 lead & PM MKZ and WP 1 lead & 4eu+ policy officer Elena del Giorgio (Univ. of Milano) have since October 2020, before TRAIN4EU started in January 2021 (M 1), been members of the R&I subgroup of Forum of European Universities FOR-EU1, a network of the 17 first generation EUA. Isabelle Kratz, 4eu+ Secretary-General, joined the R&I subgroup in February 2021. She is also member of the FOR-EU core group, allowing continuous exchange of information on EUA network activities within 4eu+.

Regular virtual meetings are held in the subgroup, which include coordinators and representatives from first generation SwafS projects, to discuss issues of common concern and plan joint activities and initiatives re. EC / DG RTD and EUAs. DG RTD and REA representatives have also regularly participated in meetings, most notably Stijn Delauré, policy officer from RTD G2 / Academic R&I and Research organisations. In these focused meetings, invited guests from EC / DG RTD and REA update the group on relevant policy domains, and discuss issues of relevance to EUA R&I dimensions.

Participation in FOREU1 paves the way for closer collaboration with EUAs by providing useful insight into projects and positions. It allows for sharing intelligence on SwafS activities and future outcomes, as well as for direct exchanges on the SwafS projects with the European Commission. Central topics discussed within the FOR-EU R&I subgroup include evaluations of the H2020 SwafS-32 TMs as part of the EU led co-creation process of funding instruments for the rollout of European universities, as well as the dissemination of project outcomes internally and across partner institutions as well as externally to national policymakers, business sectors, civic society and the European Commission.

Subtask 6.2.3: Producing 2 ERA policy briefs on R&I support function transformations

WP6 coordinates work on the two ERA policy briefs to be submitted as D7.6 (M18) and D7.7 (M36). WP6 is responsible for the main content development, in collaboration with WP1-WP5 & WP7.

The policy briefs, based in part on WP 1-6 deliverables outlining pathways for R&I transformations and the vital role universities play in Europe, aim to contribute to future policy development concerning EUAs, and to provide insights and input to policy recommendations about the future of European universities to internal and external stakeholders and decision makers, particularly the EC.

To ensure that the policy briefs are aligned with 4eu+ alliance level strategies and activities, WP6 lead & PM MKZ regularly participates in internal 4eu+ alliance meetings, including in the 4eu+ management committee, as well as in cross alliance meetings as part of the work in Task 6.2.

D7.6 ERA Policy brief 1

TRAIN4EU (ERA) Policy Brief 1 was submitted as Deliverable 7.6 in M18. The policy brief consisted of 2 main sections, as per the template furnished by REA: feedback on progress and policy recommendations. Both sections were based on mapping of common drivers of, obstacles for, and solutions to challenges and collaborations in R&I support functions emerging from cases selected for best practice assessment and innovations in WP1-WP5, framed within the Horizon2020 SwafS-32 call Transformation Modules. The cases were in the process of being analysed and potentially piloted within the project at the time of submission (M18), and as such, D7.6 constituted work in progress within TRAIN4EU.

D7.7 ERA Policy brief 2

D7.7 TRAIN4EU (ERA) Policy Brief 2 is, like D7.6 Policy Brief 1, based on a template furnished by REA. It will seek to encapsulate TRAIN4EU's commitment to develop a framework for facilitating collaboration on, and possible implementation of, future institutional transformations of selected R&I support functions within 4eu+, as well as across and beyond European University Alliances. D7.7 will be aligned with EC actions, monitorings and mappings, as well as with 4eu+ strategies and the Erasmus+ funded 1CORE project. D7.7 is due M36, after submission of the present report (M35).

3. TRAIN4EU post-project pathways

D6.2, WP6's final report, attempts to give an overview of task 6.2 initiated or supported meetings with other EUAs, showcasing shared experiences, mutual learnings and joint collaborations in WP1-WP5. Please refer to D1.3-D5.3 for more detailed descriptions of these collaborative encounters.

To fulfill WP6's objectives of boosting intra-alliance as well as inter-alliance collaboration, developing sustainable support for project outcomes is needed both in terms of continued organizational support from partner universities as well as in terms of further funding to anchor project outcomes. In the post-project phase, TRAIN4EU project members will therefore be looking at various ways to secure sustainable support for project outcomes with no EU continuation or external funding.

Discussions are already under way in the final months of the project, including at a WP lead plenary meeting hosted by Univ. of Warsaw on 19 September 2023. Topics discussed included the unsuccessful Horizon Europe WIDERA proposal BRIDGE4EU (101136850), submitted in April 2023. A main issue emerging from the discussions was the lack of continued Horizon Europe funding for R&I activities in EUAs, acting as a major obstacle to boosting collaboration within and between alliances.

For example, WP 3 on Sharing Research Infrastructure highlighted that important networking and shared experience on management and practice of research infrastructure facilities resulted from the Conference on Educational and Research Infrastructure on 8 June 2022 (see MS 5 above). Further collaboration is greatly dependent on further funding, which is not available in TRAIN4EU. Thus, the existing networks are prone to decrease in the future, as the research dimension will only be one aspect of the Alliance cooperation in the future. The WP 3 paper “*Navigating the Frontier: Research Infrastructures, Core Facilities and the Shaping of a New Paradigm at European Universities*” is currently under review for publication. It sums up the results of the work done by the project group in TRAIN4EU, including challenges and opportunities for future collaboration. The implementation of these results can only be achieved with sufficient funding.

Investment pathways for R&I dimensions of EUAs

Securing funding to make EUAs sustainable is crucial to all collaboration dimensions within alliances. Addressing this crucial issue, 4eu+ delivered input to DG EAC on Investment pathways post-2027 on 30th Sept. 2023. In terms of Research and Innovation, it outlined recommendations based in part on experiences from TRAIN4EU and the BRIDGE4EU proposal, which built on TRAIN4EU outcomes. The section ‘Background on Research & Innovation dimension’ is included here, as funding is pivotal for developing sustainable collaboration on R&I support function transformations within and between EUAs, which is ultimately WP6’s objective. It encapsulates the challenges faced by WP 6 in delivering on its WP objectives, as outlined above:

Alliances provide universities with the unique opportunity to set up stable R&I collaborations within increasingly integrated contexts thereby potentially raising excellence as well as fostering researchers and support staff mobility. So far, the SwafS projects funded under the Horizon 2020 call “Support for the Research and Innovation of European Universities” have granted Alliances a framework and funding for strengthening their R&I strategic dimension and fostering institutional transformation. Yet:

- *the projects’ timeline, which did not match the one of the Erasmus+ projects, proved challenging in creating the needed alignment between education and research projects and did not facilitate synergies across the universities’ missions as strong as we would have wished.*
- *the SwafS’s institutional capacity-building approach did not allow funding of actual R&I activities. Therefore, while the projects have led to significant results, they have not facilitated the involvement of the academic community and the testing/embedding of pilot activities.*
- *even if providing alliances with a basis for working on a number of institutional research issues, the SwafS projects also revealed that the time scale was too limited. 3 years to identify, develop, pilot test and begin implementation of a wide range of novel processes including trans-alliance collaborations is, in our view, too little time.*

Additionally, whilst no tailored continuation funding was foreseen under Horizon Europe, the recent results of the WIDERA EEI Call show how the vast majority of first wave alliances will face a two year gap with regard to R&I dedicated funding. This comes at the risk of having substantial difficulties in advancing collaboration at the same pace across the universities’ missions.

